
BUDGET SYSTEM REFORM STRATEGY OF PUBLIC FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT REFORM PROGRAM IN CAMBODIA 2005-2025

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Abstract: The Royal Government of Cambodia (RCG) has launched the Public Financial Management Reform Program (PFMRP) in 2004 with the objective to transform the public financial management system of Cambodia step-by-step to meet the international best practices and standards. The PFMRP has been designed as a comprehensive and long-term undertaking, sequenced in four platforms and four stages. The first stage (2005-2008) of the reform focused on the first platform on increasing budget credibility the second stage (2009-2015) focused on the second platform on increasing financial accountability, while further enhancing the achievements of the first platform and preparing the foundation for the third platform; the third stage (2016-2020) focused on the third platform on establishing budget-policy linkages, while further strengthening the achievements of the first two platforms and paving the way for implementing the fourth platform. The fourth stage (2021-2025) has been focusing on the primarily on building the fourth platform of public financial management reform program, increasing performance accountability, while further strengthening the achievements of the three previous platforms. The law on Public Financial System, adopted in 2008, paved the way for the budget system reform with the introduction of Budget Strategic Plan (BSP) and the piloting of Program Budgeting. In June 2013, the RGC approved the “Concept Note for Strategic Direction of Cambodia’s Budget System Reform 2013-2020” to guide and direct the implementation of Stage 3 of the PFMRP. The Concept Note is a key document for steering budget system reforms to date.

Keywords: Concepts And Conditions, Implementation Process, And Significant Positive Points Of The Budget System Reform Strategy Of Public Financial Management Reform Program Tep In Cambodia 2005-2025.

Introduction: The Concept Note for Strategic Direction of Cambodia’s Budget System Reform 2013-2020 sets out the objectives of gradual changes from “an input based and centralized budget system towards a performance based and decentralized budget system” by 2020. With this goal, the Concept Noted sets out the objectives and scope of the reforms under the framework of the budget cycle namely budget formulation, approval, execution and performance monitoring and evaluation. Up to this point, the objectives and scope related to the first three stages are generally still appropriate in the current context of the Financial System Reform. Particularly, the establishment of a performance monitoring and evaluation system as an objective of Stage 4 there is not much activity yet. However, the findings on the experiences in the implementation of program and performance budgeting from the study visits to other countries that implement program and performance budgeting pointed out the necessity to review the objectives and the scope of the reforms to be appropriate with current best international practices. Particularly for budget system at the sub-national level, the Concept Noted Pointed to the reform directions aligned with the national budget system as follows:

The objective of the sub-national policy needs to be aligned with the national policy objectives/priorities and in accordance with the administrative management structure that defines the roles, authority, and the responsibilities of sub-national administration.

- Gradual changes of the budget cycle of the sub-national administration need to be aligned with the national budget cycle.
- The financial accounting system and management of the sub-national administration needs to be aligned with the national level by using the same budget classification, chart of accounts and

reporting formats. For this direction, the finding from the studies suggested that the objectives and scope of the reforms in the sub-national budget system remain valid and relevant and do not need any revision.

In order to achieve the objectives of the Budget System Reform 2020, the RGC shall set out a number of strategics, such as the strengthening and improving the effectiveness of the Budget Strategic Plan (BSP), extending the implementation of the Piloting of Program Budgeting, launching Budget Entities, implementing a new budget classification along with the revised chart of accounts, as well as, enhancing and expanding the implementation of the FMIS, coupled with the preparation for the implementation of a performance-based budget system from year 2020 onward. Overall, this Concept Note proved useful in guiding budget system reforms based on a step by step and gradual implementation approach in line with PFMRP and up to now it is proved to be in the right direction. This kind of approach provided sufficient time for changes in the budget system and enabled all stakeholders to learn and gain practical experiences from one stage to another.

Literature Review: A Budget System Reform Strategy BSRS of Public Financial Management Reform Program (PFMRP) is a long-term mechanism of the Royal Government of Cambodia (RGC) to examines the process of budget system reform required to move from traditional, centralized input-oriented systems to more modern best practices, devolved, performance-based systems. It identifies a strategy based on recent attempts at this reform in emerging market economics and stresses the required sequencing of steps in this process. The BSRS is concepting to stress the need to progress on all three fronts simultaneously on Ministries, Line-Ministry (LM) and base these reforms on a firm platform management skill. It highlights the need to attain some basic PFMRP thresholds in the area of restructuring the budget and its classification system, to improve the accounting system, to develop a financial Management information system (FMIS), and to strengthen internal financial management skills (BSRS-2018-2025). Otherwise, The BSRS concept is based on the Law on Public Finance System, adopted in 2008, paved the way for the budget system reform with the introduction of Budget Strategic Plan (BSP) and the piloting of Program Budgeting of the Royal Government of Cambodia, Public Financial Management Reform Programmed, Stage-2, Building on Improved Budget Credibility toward Achieving Better Financial Accountability (RGC-2010). In Jun 2013, the RGC approved the “Concept Noted for Strategic Direction of Cambodia’s Budget System Reform 2013-2020” to guide and direct the implementation of Stage 3 “Budget-Policy Linkages” of the PFMRP based on the previous Phase 1 and Phase 2. The Concept Note is a key document for steering budget system reforms to date. The implementation over the last three years, especially after the piloting of full-fledge Program Budgeting in some Line Ministries (LMs), the RGC has a better understanding about the challenges in the implementation of Performance Budgeting (PB). During that time, the management, and senior officials of MEF undertook study visits to a number of selected countries to gain insights from their experiences in the application of performance budgeting. The knowledge gained from these study visits, coupled with the findings of the Program Budgeting Review, have drawn an overall conclusion that the Strategic Direction of Budget System Reform of Cambodia needs to be adjusted to become more realistic and practical. This Chapter reviews the relevant objectives of the current Concept Note, the experiences, and lesions from practical implementation from other countries, the justification for a move toward performance informed budgeting in 2025, and an explanation of the strategic objectives of 2018-2025 Budget System. The Concept Note for Strategic Direction of Cambodia’s Budget System Reform 2013-2020 sets out the objectives of gradual changes from “an input based and centralized budget system towards a performance based and decentralized budget system” by 2020. With this goal, the Concept Note sets out the objectives and scope of the reforms under the framework of the budget cycle namely budget formulation, approval, execution and performance monitoring and evaluation. Up to this point, the objectives and scope related to the first three stages are generally still appropriate in the current context of the Financial Management System Reform Program. Particularly, the establishment of a performance monitoring and evaluation system as an objective of Stage 4 there is not much activity yet. However, the findings on the experiences in the implementation of program and performance budgeting from the study visits to other country that implement program and performance budgeting pointed out

the necessity to review the objectives and the scope of the reforms to be appropriate with current best international practices.

Objectives: The Objectives of the present research are specifically: (i) to explain the basic concepts and conditions of the Budget System Reform Strategy of Public Financial Management Reform Program, (ii) to discuss about the implementation process of the Budget System Reform Strategy of Public Financial Management Reform Program, and (iii) to discuss about the significance positive points for further improvement of the Budget System Reform Strategy of Public Financial Management Reform Program in Cambodia 2005-2025.

Methodologies: The research has used both descriptive and quantitative approaches to answer the research questions, meet the objectives and test the hypotheses. In descriptive approach, the research has relied on relevant literatures on PFMRP and the policies of the government of Cambodia. In the Quantitative approach, the research has used necessary tables, graphs, and statistical models for the analysis of the data. The research is confined to the discussion on 9 General Departments, namely, (i)-General Department of Economy and Finance Policy, (ii)-General Secretariat, (iii)-General Department of Budget, (iv)-General Department of Sub-National Administration Finance, (v)-General Department of Public Procurement, (vi)-General Department of Customs and Excise, (vii)-General Department of Taxation, (viii)-General Department of National Treasury, (ix)-The General Secretariat, in each 10 Departments and 23 Line-Ministry which were fully operated during the time of research, have been selected for the research purposes. It has reviewed relevant changing basic concepts during implementation period of the Budget System Reform Strategy (BSRS) and the implementation process in doing BSRS and the significant positive points BSRS of PFMRP in Cambodia.

Discussions: Up on the Royal Government of Cambodia's conceptual and objectives of PFMRP in Cambodia 2005-2025; the main concepts: public entities were mostly insufficient performance, leaders were mostly using centralization system, financial management system were poorly performed, Cambodia social revolutions were always changing; the main objectives to build an efficient accountability and transparent national budget system. To meet the study objectives, data presentation and analysis were divided into two parts. The first part analysis the finding of the field survey which contained the profile of sample respondents as well as detailed primary data analysis concerning the main objectives of the research. The second part noted the concepts and conditions, implementation, and significant positive points for improvement the BSRS of PFMRP in Cambodia 2005-2025.

The Reformation System Status: period of the BSRS of PFMRP in Cambodia 2005-2025, the research study has done surveyed up on the scope and limitation of research and based on sample size, sampling method, data gathering procedures, statistical tools, and the procedures of analyzing data; According to the Table 5.1 (The Reformation System Status) showed the status of Budget System Reform Strategy in each category has been doing PFMRP as all ongoing process from all studied participants with the status of ongoing reforms and consist of government and grant projects fund. These two sources of funding cover all planned reform according to the data from this study. The reformation level has been dividing into regional and sub-regional levels, with 119 (71.7%) participating, regional level, Sub-Regional level, Across finance/treasury offices only at 46 (27.7%), Sub-Regional level, Across finance/treasury offices only at 1 (0.6%).

Table 5.1

The Reformation System Status Items	Frequency	Percent
Budget System Reform Strategy in doing PFMRP		
Ongoing	166	100.0
Total	166	100.0
Ongoing reforms/planned reforms		
Government fund & Grant	166	100.0
Total	166	100.0
Reformation Level		
Regional level, Sub-Regional level	119	71.7

Regional level, Sub-Regional level, Across finance/treasury offices only	46	27.7
Sub-Regional level, Across finance/treasury offices only	1	0.6
Total	166	100

Table 5.2

The Concepts of PFMRP in Cambodia Concepts/Reasons	Frequency	Percent
1. The public entities are mostly insufficient performed, 2. The Cambodia social revolutions are always changing. 3. The leaders are mostly using a centralization system. 4. The financial management system is poorly performed.	1	0.6
1. The public entities are mostly insufficient performed, 2. The Cambodia social revolutions are always changing. 3. The leaders are mostly using centralization system, 4. The financial management system is poorly performed.	165	99.4
Total	166	100.0

Source: Own Survey

Figure 5.1 : The Concepts of PFMRP in Cambodia

Source: Own Survey

Note: Table 5.2 and Figure 5.1 indicate percentage to the respondents.

In accordance with Table 5.3 (The Aims of PFMRP in Cambodia 2005-2025) displayed the data on the aims of the Cambodia Budget System Reform Strategies 2005-2025 in the PFMRP from participants, who all agreed on four main objectives as follows:

- 1) Keep strengthening budget credibility by strengthening management of revenue, debt, and cash, and improving budget execution.
- 2) Continue strengthening financial accountability through improved budget classification implementation, launching the new budget and operations systems, strengthening the reporting system and financial accountability, and enhancing the functions of internal audit.
- 3) Focus on budget-policy linkages by rolling out full program budgeting and covering more budget entities, improving budget comprehensiveness and integration, defining clear roles and responsibilities of MEF line ministries and legislative bodies, developing a medium-term expenditure

- framework (MTEF), developing a monitoring and evaluation (M&E) system, and implementing financial decentralization.
- 4) Prepare the foundation for the introduction of performance accountability, including the performance budgeting framework, defining lines of performance budget accountability, launching the performance auditing framework, and developing a capacity development plan.
 - 5) Support the reform program by building capacity, incentivizing the reform, and strengthening the capacity for performing each Stage.

Table 5.3: The Aims of PFMRP in Cambodia 2005-2025

The Aims	Frequency	Percent
1,2,3,4,5	166	100.0

Source: Own Survey

The reasons for Financial Management Information System (FMIS) playing an important role in doing Budget System Reform Strategy of PFMRP from all respondents were found in table 5.4 (Reasons of FMIS Plays an Important Role in PFMRP) and divided into six main points:

- i Customizable functional tools with budget system program,
- ii Customizable functional tools with Ministries and Line-ministry,
- iii Controllable cash on hand, cash advanced, and cash in bank.
- iv Controllable monthly and annual revenues and expenditures,
- v Producibile on financial reports with more optional in details,
- vi Fit able with the objectives of PFMRP of the government.

The fundamental concepts of Budget System Reform Strategy began with RGC and Partners by using the government funds and grants, with most practices occurring at the regional and sub-regional levels. Keeping with the purpose of PFMRP, nearly all participants were aware of the factors underlying and causing the reformation. The concepts of government reformation were well understood by the participants. The study discovered that the understanding of doing PFMRP reformation was due to previous insufficient performance, social changes and revolution, prior use of centralization, and poor performance in Financial Management Information System (FMIF). The objectives of doing Cambodia Budget System Reform Strategies 2005-2025 in PFMRP has been discovered to be a great awareness in this study. According to the findings of the study, the objectives were classified into four categories:

- 1) Maintain budget credibility by improving revenue, debt, and cash management and improving budget execution.
- 2) Maintain financial accountability by improving budget classification implementation, launching new budget and operations systems, strengthening the reporting system and financial accountability, and enhancing internal audit functions.
- 3) Focus on budget-policy linkages by rolling out full program budgeting and covering more budget entities, improving budget comprehensiveness and integration, defining clear roles and responsibilities of MEF line ministries and legislative bodies, developing a medium-term expenditure framework (MTEF), developing a monitoring and evaluation (M&E) system, and implementing financial decentralization.
- 4) Prepare the foundation for the introduction of performance accountability, including the performance budgeting framework, defining lines of performance budget accountability, launching the performance auditing framework, and developing a capacity development plan. Support the reform program by building capacity, incentivizing the reform, and strengthening the capacity for the implementation of Stage.

Furthermore, the study discovered that almost all participants have a good understanding of why the government is implementing the Budget System Reform Strategy (BSRS) and why applying the Financial Management Information System (FMIS) plays an important role in implementing the PFMRP 2005-2025.

Table 5.4 : Reasons of FMIS Plays an Important Role of BSRS in PFMRP

Reason	Frequency	Percent
1. Customizable functional tools with budget system program, 2. Customizable functional tools with Ministries and Line-ministry, 3. Controllable cash on hand, cash advanced, and cash in bank, 4. Controllable on monthly and annually revenues and expenditures, 5. Producibile on financial reports with more optional in details, 6. Fit able with the objectives of PFMRP of government	166	100.0
Total	166	100.0

Figure 5.2 : Reasons of FMIS Plays an Important Role in PFMRP

Source: Own Survey

Note: Table 5.4 and Figure 5.2 indicate percentage to the respondents.

In accordance with the references of supporting documents and data research studied on the Table 5.1 to the Table 5.4, there has been mentioning clearly that the basic concepts and conditions of the Budget System Reform Strategy of Public Financial Management Reform Program in Cambodia 2005-2025 as below:

- 1) The Public Financial Management Reform Program is a long-term reform program with an ambitious and realistic vision of transforming Cambodia’s Public Financial System toward international best practices, by building and strengthening the four core components including: Improve the System, Legal Framework, Institutions Mechanisms, and Human Resources. The Public Financial Management Reform Program is to be organized in accordance with the context of socio-economic development.
- 2) The Public Financial Management Reform Program was launched under the leadership of Samdach Akka Moha Sena Padey Techo Hun Sen, Prime Minister of Kingdom of Cambodia, on 05th December 2004 by taking the approach and dividing it into four stages, including:
First Stage: “budget credibility” (2005-2008),
Second Stage: “enhancing financial accountability” (2009-2014), Third Stage: “establishing budget-policy linkage” (2015-2020), Fourth Stage: “performance accountability” (2021-2025).
- 3) In this regard, the Budget System Reform Strategy of Public Financial Management Reform Program is being implemented in the fourth phase of the PFM Reform Program. The Steering Committee for PFM Reform Program has set out the three priority goals, including:
 - Strengthening the Management and Implementation of Revenues Collection Plans,
 - Strengthening and Expending the Deployment of Information Technology Systems (FMIS) for PFM Reform Program and

- Strengthening and Expanding the Implementation Program Budgets, as well as providing funding to support the implementation of action plans to the reform team.

The Significant Positive Points for Further Improvement of the BSRS of PFMRP in Cambodia 2005-2025 : In accordance with the descriptive of the Major Concerns or Risk Associated with the Reformation of data analyzing, there has been summarizing that the significant positive points of the BSRS of PFRMP in Cambodia 2005-2025 included:

First, to building the foundation of the credibility of the budget by strengthening the mechanism of revenue collection of the state budget, as well as the effective management of expenditures and the management of public debt, especially the complete elimination of Chronic congested debt. In addition, the increase in current revenue has enabled the Royal Government of Cambodia to increase expenditures to improve the quality and expand the scope of public services in order to bring public services closer to the people.

Second, the achievement of the core mechanism of financial accountability through the implementation of the information technology system for applying on the Public Financial Management Reform Program (FMIS) within the Ministry of Economy and Finance and by Ministries and Institutions. The strengthening of the internal audit function at the ministries and institutions and the organization of the amendment and enforcement of the law and the relevant legal provisions of future budget management, FMIS will be the core mechanism to strengthen the efficiency. Budget and financial accountability at all levels, both at the level of financial oversight, level of cash management and level of performance.

Third, the achievement of linking the budget to the policy by implementing the full program budget in all Ministries and institutions and in the capital-provincial administrations. In this implementation effort, budget preparation and negotiation have been further strengthened and positively improved by better reflecting key policy priorities of the government.

Fourth, further improvements in the dissemination of budget information through the provision of budget information since the preparation of the macroeconomic framework, the adoption and implementation of the annual financial law for the efficiency, accountability, and transparency of the budget.

Fifth, achieving high economic growth with equitable distribution of growth and maintaining overall macroeconomic stability. In fact, achieving high economic growth of around 7% per year and strong macroeconomic conditions in the context of low inflation and stable exchange rates, as well as the positive results of PFM Reform Program, have made people Cambodia at all levels, including civil servants, the armed forces, and the general Cambodians throughout the country, has the opportunity to increase their income to support their respective families with a hopefully life.

It is concluded that there were significant clearly stated directly and indirectly from the Royal Government of Cambodia (RGC) and Senior Minister, Secretariate of State, Under Secretariate of State, General Director, Deputy General Director, International Consultants, Officials and from the results of research surveyed on the basis concept, implementation process, and the significant improvement of Budget System Reform Strategy of Public Financial Management Reform Program as briefly described below:

- 1) The last 18-year journey to date in implementing the PFMRP has been satisfying, particularly the essential progress in platforms and stages 1, 2, and 3 as well as the good progress made in the implementation of platform 4 in 2021-2025. Up on the publication by MEF and research study, performance budgeting can categorize into three models as follow:
 - Presentational Performance Budgeting: In this model, performance information is illustrated in budget documents or other government documents. Performance information refers to target or result or both and it is included as background information for accountability and for discussion

with legislators and the public-on-public policies. Such performance information does not have any formal impact over the decisions made in the budgeting process.

- Performance Informed Budgeting: In this model, budget resource preparations are indirectly linked to the proposed performance or past achievements by ministries and government agencies. Performance information has an important role, but does not have a pre-determined weight, nor being an absolute factor for making decisions on budget allocation. In this sense, performance information is not the only basis, but it needs to be used along with other information related to political and economic aspects and policy priorities for decision making on budget or resource allocation.
- Direct Performance Budgeting or Performance Based budgeting: In this model, resource allocation is made directly and explicitly based on the unit of performance to be achieved, generally referring to outputs achieved in the year.

After being officially launched in 2004, the progress of PFMRP was slow in the first few years of its implementation as MEF required time to understand and

- 2) absorb the new concepts and knowledge, study the new systems evolving as international best practice, draw on its own practical experiences as well as experiences from those countries which have taken steps well ahead of Cambodia, and balance all of these to best fit into the Cambodia context. The pace of reforms accelerated, particularly in the last over 18 years as the pre-requisites for the implementation of program, which is the core element of the reforms in Stage 3, were essentially completed, and the progress made in institutionalizing them. At the same time, LMs and institutions gained better understanding and adapted to the new concepts and ideas, in particular, the importance of the linkages between budget and policy.
- 3) Under the long-term vision of the RGC to become an upper middle-income country by 2030 and higher income by 2050, the PFMRP can be considered as a determinant, while the budget systems reform will be a key tool to achieve this vision. Therefore, the PFMRP will continue to play a critical and core reform agenda for achieving platform 4 objectives by 2025. However, in the coming years, the budget systems reform will likely face some major challenges. First, the reform agenda was too optimistic and unrealistic, while understanding of the value of reform and the path to achieve them is still limited. Second, the pace of reforms between the national budget system and other related key areas of reforms is not in tandem with and pace of one another and inter-linked. Third, human capital and institutional capacity development does not match with full-blown reforms, and this will take a longer time-frame, more resources, and mutual willingness from stakeholders, especially from all the leaders of LMs and institutions. Fourth, the reform process is dynamic as international practices are also evolving in an ever-changing global landscape.

Conclusion: Overall, this Strategy outlines ambitious goals and at the same time shows the major risks which could be encountered during its implementation. Nevertheless, Cambodia must overcome them to achieve its goals. This is consistent with the current situation, where Cambodia has reached the stage of development and the new trends in international public financial management. Leadership and ownership of key stakeholders along with valuable knowledge support from the Development Partners (DPs), are the key factors that will contribute to the success of the Budget System Reform. More precisely, the resolute support and guidance from Prime Minister, Samdach Akka Moha Sena Padei Techo Hun Sen, Prime Minister of the Kingdom of Cambodia, the Commander-in-Chief, has provided accelerated momentum to make PFM an outstanding success. This factor will no doubt provide hope to Cambodia to implement the Budget System Reform with effectiveness, accountability, and transparency toward achieving the goal of 2025 in line with best international practice.

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